

Efficacy of the elementary, middle, and high school students' persuasive speech: Evidence from South Korea

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to analyze the efficacy of elementary, middle, and high school students with respect to using persuasive speech and establish a direction for the development of relevant education. It examines the case of South Korea, where the government has presented the importance of persuasive speech education and implemented considerable measures since 2015. It utilizes the survey results on the perception around persuasive speech, based on the achievement standard set within the Korean language curriculum for elementary, middle, and high school students. The research offers several recommendations. First, it is necessary to specify educational content so that it applies differentially, according to the conditions of students. Second, educational content that addresses students' attitudes, self-awareness, and participation in community issues must be reinforced. Third, educational content related to persuasion preparation, content organization methods, strategies, and meta-cognitive aspects must be presented sequentially in terms of beginning, development, and application, as suited to each level of education. Fourth, it is necessary to review the teaching-learning methods to increase the effectiveness of persuasive speech education. Fifth, it is necessary to especially consider the disadvantages of middle school students, who have huge gaps in efficacy with respect to their knowledge of persuasive speech.

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1. INTRODUCTION

At present, most countries face multiple social conflicts due to growing divisions and disunities. To resolve such conflicts, many countries emphasize the cultivation of their citizens' democratic virtues. These virtues are summarized as tolerance, reconciliation, magnanimity, and understanding [1]. In order to exert such virtues and resolve social conflicts, moderating and mitigating differential opinions through conversations and deliberations are required. This process cannot be carried out unless there is "persuasion" of others, as persuasion is a fundamental and vital function of discourse for the members of a modern society [2], [3].

The perspective on the influence of persuasion has been expanded from an individual's internal cognitive change to the formation of a social opinion or attitude change [4]. In particular, in recent years, various methods of persuasion through social media have affected exposure to political opinions and political views [5]. In the age of social media, opinion leaders also try to change other people's political or social attitudes and behaviors through various media [6].

Recently, with the development of artificial intelligence, studies have been conducted on the structure and aspects of persuasion through artificial intelligence as a medium, or to clarify the difference between human persuasion and persuasion by artificial intelligence [7], [8]. However, artificial intelligence is designed and created by humans; the fact that the target of persuasion is human does not change [9], [10]. Therefore, to explore the essence of persuasion, attention must be paid to aspects, such as human attitudes and affective areas [11].

In addition, the process of collective attitude change through persuasion can be explained by Festinger's social comparison theory, which is based on the fact that people make efforts to become similar to others with the motive to compare their abilities and opinions with others [12]. This can be explained in association with the congruity theory and cognitive dissonance theory, which deal with the balance and imbalance between the narrator (oneself), listener (the other), and the target of persuasion. In particular, the congruity theory quantifies how much an individual (narrator) likes the object and other (listener) with attitude, thereby determining an internally balanced and consistent state. The congruity theory and cognitive dissonance theory explain the voluntary cause of collective attitude change. Constant internal persuasion occurs in this process of attitude change, and implicit persuasion occurs in various ways within society.

Persuasion in society plays a crucial role in not only voluntary collective attitude change as mentioned by the congruity theory and cognitive dissonance theory, but also passive collective attitude change seen in 'group polarization' and 'conformity theory' [13]. Group polarization is a phenomenon in which decisions in a group with people who have similar attitudes are made in an extreme way, showing that people take the same attitude towards matters that have important value to the group in the interaction process for comparison with others [14]. The conformity effect is how a group's opinion is formed with a single piece of information in cases with no answers or in ambiguous situations [15]. Group polarization and conformity may be regarded as obedience to the group's pressure or absolute power on the surface, but the results come from multilateral persuasions among individuals or between individuals and society.

As such, persuasion is conducted not only in an individual's internal situation as a cognitive process but also when exchanging opinions or affecting awareness within the society to which the individual belongs [16]. Thus, persuasive competence has a crucial effect on individual aspects, as well as social aspects when considering the community. Moreover, the persuasive competence is not developed by drilling fragmentary skills or knowledge, but requires various aspects to be considered, such as one's relationship with the target of persuasion, their socio-cultural background, and the given context. It is an ability that can be nurtured by constant and systematic education. In this context, this paper focuses on the increasing importance of competence in persuasive speech in modern society and aims to establish a direction for educational content on the same for elementary, middle, and high school students. To this end, as will be discussed later in detail, it closely examines the case of South Korea (henceforth Korea) based on a survey on the perception around persuasive speech.

With the 2015 revision of the national curriculum, the Korean Government emphasized the core competencies necessary for the future and established the primary goal of education as "developing an individual with the ability to smoothly communicate with other members as a social self in a speech community". Furthermore, based on competence-based education, they conceptualized a desirable character as "an individual that can effectively reveal his or her opinions by living in harmony within the community." There were four competences required for this desirable human character: i) Competence in communication; ii) Competence in community and personal relations; iii) Competence in enjoying culture; and iv) Competence in introspection and self-improvement. Among them, "competence in communication" is the "competence to effectively express one's thoughts and emotions in various situations, communicate with others and mediate conflicts" [17].

The national curriculum of Korea is striving to keep pace with the rapidly changing trend that emphasizes the importance of persuasive competence. Furthermore, institutional efforts have been made to ensure the persuasive competence of students since 2015, which is relatively recent. Therefore, the case of Korea is expected to provide important implications for developing the persuasive competence of students and nurturing democratic citizens.

Moreover, considering recent research trends on persuasive communication, this paper aims to offer practical implications of learning and teaching persuasive skills. Recent studies regarding persuasive communication include the effect of unstable and imperfect communication on persuasion [18], the central role of subjective valuation in persuasion and social influence for both propagators and receivers of influence [19], the study on whether populist appeals elicit emotions and whether this increases the persuasiveness of the appeals [20], the effect that health narratives have on persuasion [21], the algorithmic persuasion framework in online communication [22]. Thus, recent research trends related to persuasive communication focus on the process and results of persuasion based on various communication methods. However, this study is notable in that it took the learner who is the subject of persuasion as the research object. Therefore, this paper aims to answer the following questions: i) What are the perceptions of Korean learners about

persuasion?; ii) Is there a difference in the efficacy of elementary, middle, and high school learners' persuasion speech?; and iii) What are the implications of this analysis for the development of persuasive speech education content for enhancing communication skills?

Thus, this study covered theoretical discussions on competence in persuasive speech in the following section. In the middle of the article, the perception of persuasive speech prevalent among elementary, middle, and high school students in cognitive, affective, and social aspects is discussed. This discussion will be based on a survey on the aforementioned perception based on the achievement standard set by the Korean language curriculum for elementary, middle, and high school students in the country. Finally, according to research findings, it analyzes the current state of persuasive speech education, identifies areas for improvement in Korea, and establishes a direction for the development of desirable persuasive speech education for the future.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Persuasive competence

Persuasion is the process of gaining sympathy from the target of persuasion or receiving a persuasive message from them [7]. Moreover, persuasive competence is the ability to bring change to the object of persuasion through a series of processes designed with the intention to bring about such change. Thus, persuasive competence, which selects and uses appropriate means and strategies of persuasion to create the content and induce the other's sympathy and response by effectively expressing the content, has a complicated character, and thus the following three aspects must be considered.

2.2. Consideration of persuasive competence

2.2.1. Cognitive process of the persuader

The psychological view of persuasion emphasizes the importance of "cognition" in the process. Depending on the importance of the message, the process in which the information is processed varies, and accordingly, the results of persuasion appear differently. In the past, the cognitive process of persuasion was viewed as an individual difference (personal motivation, ability, and interest). However, in the process of cognitively processing persuasion, intervention from the external environment may affect it [23].

2.2.2. "Attitude" change of the other

Most sociologists claim that "attitude" directs human behavior. Thus, many theories of persuasion focus on "attitude." Katz [24] classified the psychological functions that determine attitudes as the instrumental (adjective, utilitarian) function, ego-defensive function, knowledge function, and value-expressive function. The discussion about "attitude" has been implemented to understand and explain human behavior, but attitudes are in many cases impossible to observe directly, highly complicated, and not easy to measure. However, "attitude" changes in persuasion directly affect the results of persuasion such as cognition, emotions, beliefs, and behaviors. Thus, it is necessary to have the ability to establish and implement specific persuasive strategies to understand the psychological functions within attitudes and effectively change them.

In the process of persuasion, a new attitude is formed or an existing attitude is reinforced or changed to a different one depending on the purpose, context, or type of discourse. Thus, persuasive competence is the ability to establish strategies while capturing others' attitude changes, predict their responses in the process of persuasion, and adequately deal with their unexpected responses. To improve persuasive competence, it is necessary to provide education that holistically considers many aspects under the various contexts of persuasion, such as the type of response, factors shaping the listener's attitude, the attitude shaping process, the reason for attitude shaping, evaluation of attitude, and factors to predict and consider future actions.

2.2.3. Social expansiveness

Changes in individual perspectives or attitudes may affect changes in society, but public opinion or atmosphere based on socio-cultural foundations may affect changes in individual attitudes. People make choices to maximize the value they expect from their actions, and in the process, self-relevance, social involvement, weekly values, and various socio-cultural factors affect them [19]. In particular, factors that influence persuasion due to the development of social media complexly involve not only individual internal factors but also various societal factors. Therefore, it is also necessary to consider socio-cultural factors that influence persuasion or their influence. As such, persuasive competence can be seen as a more developed ability required by an individual according to social changes. Thus, it is not just an individually fixed competence but a variable one that is shaped by the socio-cultural context.

2.3. Efficacy of students

Bandura [25], [26] explained self-efficacy as the mental ability of a learner to organize and carry out the actions necessary to perform tasks and proposed the concept of “triadic reciprocity,” which states that individual factors include cognitive and physiological events and, in particular, cognitive factors that influence one’s motivation and behavior by judging one’s abilities and self-perception of the effectiveness of actions. It means that cognitive, motivational, affective, and selection processes that occur when deciding their motivation, emotion, and actions affect self-efficacy. In this paper, we try to present the cognitive process by linking cognitive efficacy and the emotional process to emotional efficacy and the selection process to social efficacy.

2.3.1. Cognitive efficacy

Cognitive efficacy has an important influence on motivation. Motivation refers to the process of instigating and sustaining goal-oriented activities, which are personal and internal influences that result in selection, effort, persistence, achievement, and environmental regulation [27]. The cognitive process that anticipates and controls events that will affect life involves a lot of uncertainty and ambiguity. Envisioning and preparing a course of action, and knowing how to use knowledge and skills in a specific situation, is done through thinking. Cognitive efficacy works in this process. Thus, cognitive efficacy can be defined as self-efficacy that operates in cognitive processes that predict the outcomes of a given event or situation, formulates rules or strategies, and structures opinions. This kind of efficacy influences analysis, strategies, and expressions, such as structuring knowledge, collecting predictable information, and expressing information appropriately.

2.3.2. Affective efficacy

The concept of emotional self-efficacy is somewhat similar to the concept of emotional regulation. This includes the ability to understand and manage inner emotions by implementing appropriate cognitive and behavioral strategies. It is a belief in the ability to improve negative emotional states concerning difficult events and manage negative emotions such as anger, irritation, despondency, and discouragement. It is also a belief in the ability to experience or express positive emotions such as joy, passion, and pride in response to successful or joyful events [28].

Self-efficacy helps predict what will happen when the anxiety factor is reduced. This implies that the affective process helps to predict how to behave in difficult situations by accepting self-efficacy and plays a role in adequately handling negative emotions such as anxiety and distrust. In this respect, affective efficacy can be regarded as a sense of efficacy relevant to emotional control, psychology, and attitude.

2.3.3. Social efficacy

Through Bandura’s theory of self-efficacy [25], [26], it is possible to understand not only the characteristics of an individual’s inner ability but also the individual’s ability to engage in social relations. Social efficacy is the belief that an individual can do something in certain situations. Social efficacy defined as people’s belief in the ability to successfully perform a given task or action in a social relationship [29].

Belief in human efficacy can be viewed as a life process that influences the choice of environment and behavior. People tend to avoid situations and actions that are regarded as being beyond their abilities. However, they are willing to challenge themselves and perform when they judge that they can handle them. According to Bandura [25], [26], by their choice, they have different competencies, interests, and social networks. In other words, self-efficacy affects the choice of individual behavior but can affect people’s lives, including their interests, value systems, and social influences. In this respect, we can say that social efficacy is considered during the selection process according to people’s lives and the situations they are confronted by, which affects the atmosphere of society and community that is outside of one’s personal boundaries.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The student perception survey was conducted from 1 July to 20 July in 2016. The researchers surveyed 375 students from elementary, middle, and high schools located in Gangbuk, the northern part of the Capital Seoul, Korea. The demographic information of research subjects is shown in Table 1.

At least 80% of the students had not received private education related to the Korean language, essay writing, and debate, and their academic achievement was at an average level. As for speaking ability (debate, presentation), private education related to the Korean language, essay writing, and debate were used as a key index for sampling based on the empirical judgment that there is a gap in the perception of students who have received private education and those who have not. Moreover, schools located in the same region were selected because perceptions about speaking ability may also vary depending on students’ level or living environment based on the region as well.

Table 1. Demographic information of the research subjects

School	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Elementary	64(57.1)	48(42.9)	112(100.0)
Middle	86(54.1)	73(45.9)	159(100.)
High	53(51.0)	51(49.0)	104(100.)
Total	203(54.1)	172(45.9)	375(100.0)

The survey was conducted on students in their final year of each school—sixth grade in elementary school, senior in middle school, and senior in high school—because the final year is when education is sufficiently completed at each school. In the student perception survey, students’ thoughts about persuasive speech were examined in a subjective, open-ended questionnaire, by presenting the educational content of persuasive speech that is valued in the curriculum and having the students rate their own competence in each area on a five-point Likert scale. It was intended to determine the students’ own perceptions of their competences in persuasive speech, or the educational content they felt they lacked or which they excelled in. This was to analyze the educational aspects and application of persuasive speech and apply them to the development of the educational content of persuasive speech.

A quantitative method was used to analyze the importance of the educational content of persuasive speech as perceived by students. Using SPSS 18.0, the analysis was conducted through frequency analysis and descriptive statistical analysis. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to verify the differences in perception between elementary, middle, and high school students.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Perception of persuasive competence

To determine elementary, middle, and high school students’ perceptions of persuasive competence, a survey was conducted on the nature of “persuasive speech” using a free-answer method. Students responded that persuasive speech is matching another’s opinion with their own and making him or her agree (48%); a means to achieve a desired purpose (27%); explaining, arguing, proving, and making others understand their opinions (18.5%); winning another’s empathy or heart (4.4%); and seeking cooperation (2.1%). Regarding when persuasion is needed, students responded in the following order overall, as shown in Table 2 (collaborative problem solving>discussion, request>campaign speech>excuse>criticism/fight). Elementary school students responded that persuasion is needed in debate, whereas middle and high school students responded that it is needed in problem solving.

Table 2. Learners’ perceptions of when persuasion is needed

	All	Elementary	Middle	High
Discussion	17.3%	39.5%	5.9%	15.0%
Collaborative problem solving	42.0%	18.5%	58.1%	39.0%
Request	17.3%	13.6%	17.6%	20.0%
Criticism/fight	4.8%	9.9%	2.2%	4.0%
Campaign speech	10.3%	9.9%	7.4%	15.0%
Excuse	8.3%	8.6%	8.8%	7.0%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

As shown in Table 3, to the question of which competence is required for effective persuasion, elementary school students responded logical reasoning/basis>fluency, while middle school students responded fluency>thinking skills=empathy/consideration. High school students responded logical reasoning/basis and fluency. They responded more with competences related to the narrator’s public confidence—such as nonverbal strategies, honesty, and trust—than other students.

Elementary school students tended to stress logical reasoning/basis more than other students. This may be due to the fact that they mostly limited the situations in which persuasive speech is needed to “discussions.” Middle school students tended to think of consideration and empathy as important, which reflects their age characteristics (the point in which they enter adolescence and begin to show full interest in human relations).

Table 3. Learners' perceptions about the required ability to persuade well

Relevant competence	All	Elementary	Middle	High
Logical reasoning/basis	33.2%	48.3%	25.0%	31.0%
Persuasion-related knowledge	9.2%	10.1%	6.6%	12.0%
Fluency	24.6%	16.9%	30.9%	23.0%
Nonverbal strategy	9.2%	5.6%	8.1%	14.0%
Empathy/consideration	17.2%	10.1%	25.0%	13.0%
Honesty/trust	5.2%	4.5%	4.4%	7.0%
Emotion regulation/control of reason	1.4%	4.5%	0.0%	0.0%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%

The overall results showed that students stressed logical reasoning/basis and fluency in persuasive competence. This is due to the fact that students perceived “persuasive competence” as an individual’s speech skills and a means to defeat others in arguments or conflicts. Because the content related to “persuasive speech” in the curricula is focused mostly on cognitive thinking—and debates as a specific discourse type are taught only in terms of competing to win or lose—students have come to perceive persuasive speech education as developing fluency, logical reasoning, and critical skills for the purpose of defeating others. This is also a result of not properly considering the influence of persuasion on society or the community, as well as the social value of persuasive speech, due to the fact that persuasive speech education has, thus far, focused only on the functional aspects of speaking or individual speaking skills, such as establishing persuasive strategies and speaking fluently.

4.2. Efficacy of persuasive speech

The researchers analyzed the efficacy of 375 elementary, middle, and high school students in persuasive speech based on the affective, cognitive, and social classifications by Lee [30]. As a result of rating persuasive competence on a five-point scale, elementary school students showed the highest score with 3.9 points, followed by middle school students with 3.3 points, and high school students with 3.1 points. This indicates that higher grades perceived lower efficacy of persuasive speech.

The researchers employed a one-way ANOVA test to determine the differences in the efficacy of persuasive speech by school level. The value was lower than the significance probability of 0.001, as shown in Table 4. This indicates that there was a clear difference in the efficacy of persuasive speech depending on the school level.

Table 4. The efficacy of persuasive speech by school level (one-way ANOVA) (Mean±SD)

School	N	Mean±SD	F-value	p-value
Elementary	101	3.87±.870	24.959	.000***
Middle	155	3.34±.775		
High	103	3.08±.882		

*p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001

Using a one-way ANOVA test to determine the differences in students’ thoughts about their persuasive competence by school (grade), the value was lower than the significance probability of 0.001, thereby indicating high significance. This indicates that there was a clear difference in persuasive competence depending on the school (grade). The group differences were determined through a Duncan’s test during the ex-post analysis. The results indicated that middle and high school students showed differences in thinking from elementary school students.

Overall, the efficacy of persuasive speech tends to decrease as the school level increases from elementary to middle and high school, and high school students, in particular, showed very low efficacy. Considering that efficacy is a belief system about anticipated achievement to perform certain activities, a decrease in efficacy can be interpreted as a decrease in competence in persuasive speech. In addition, Table 5 to Table 7 show the results of the survey on efficacy with detailed evaluation content on persuasive speech for students and cognitive, affective, and social categorization of efficacy.

In cognitive efficacy, high school students showed relatively low scores in content preparation, argument and basis, content organization, and use of media. These are competences required in the step prior to persuasive speech. This is because these competences are to make students think about their own problems, to explore and find the necessary grounds to solve the problems, and to effectively organize the content.

Table 5. The cognitive efficacy of elementary, middle, and high school learners in persuasive speech

Relevant competence	Elementary		Middle		High	Total
	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference		
Argument and basis	4.13	-0.46	3.55	-0.22	3.38	3.68
Content organization	4.10	-0.80	3.30	-0.10	3.20	3.50
Use of media	4.00	-0.80	3.20	-	3.20	3.40
Content preparation	4.07	-0.50	3.57	-0.20	3.37	3.70
Adequate expression	4.02	-0.48	3.54	-0.18	3.36	3.62
Critical analysis	4.05	-0.60	3.45	-0.20	3.25	3.60
Rule compliance	4.15	-0.60	3.55	-0.25	3.40	3.70
Persuasive strategy	4.10	-0.54	3.55	-0.19	3.25	3.65
Listener analysis	4.10	-0.55	3.60	-0.26	3.60	3.61
Mean	4.08	-0.59	3.48	-0.18	3.33	3.61

Table 6. The affective efficacy of elementary, middle, and high school learners in persuasive speech

	Elementary		Middle		High	Total
	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference		
Empathy of other	4.50	-1.00	3.50	-	3.50	3.80
Confidence	4.10	-0.50	3.60	-0.30	3.30	3.70
Appeal to emotion	3.80	-0.50	3.30	-0.20	3.10	3.40
Trust	4.00	-0.40	3.60	-0.30	3.30	3.70
Mean	4.10	-0.64	3.50	-0.18	3.30	3.65

Table 7. The social efficacy of elementary, middle, and high school learners in persuasive speech

Relevant competence	Elementary		Middle		High	Total
	Mean	Difference	Mean	Difference		
Consideration of social influence	4.10	-0.80	3.30	-0.20	3.10	3.50
Exploration of alternatives	4.00	-0.40	3.60	-0.30	3.30	3.70
Mediation of opinions	4.10	-0.30	3.80	-0.50	3.30	3.70
Mean	4.07	-0.50	3.57	-0.33	3.23	3.63

In affective efficacy, efficacy in appealing to emotions tended to be low all around. This may be caused by the emphasis on education that focuses on rational and logical persuasive strategies because, in school, persuasion is mostly taught in terms of debate. In social efficacy, content related to attitudes of discourse in a community is presented in tenth grade and higher in the curriculum, such as “Introspecting discourse customs in a speech community and having the attitude to contribute to developing a desirable communication culture, understanding the discourse customs in a speech community and having the attitude to participate in developing a sound speech culture, and understanding the value of speech and developing the attitude to communicate sincerely.” Nonetheless, higher-grade students tended to show lower scores.

As shown in Figure 1, the efficacy of persuasive speech showed a remarkable change, particularly as the school level moved from elementary to middle school, and the change was particularly great in the affective aspects. This can be associated with the results of the perception survey about the persuasive speech of middle school students (i.e., the tendency to value relational aspects such as empathy in persuasive competence). Changes in the affective aspects, among other reasons, may have played a significant role in explaining why the efficacy of persuasive speech, which had been high in elementary school, decreased remarkably in middle school.

Figure 1. Efficacy of elementary, middle, and high school students about persuasive speech

4.3. Perceptions of the detailed persuasive competence of elementary, middle, and high school students

4.3.1. Importance of persuasive competence by type of discourse

Using a one-way ANOVA test, we examined whether there was a difference in thinking about the need for persuasive competence in seven situations by school level (grade). Table 8 shows that the value was lower than the significance probability of 0.01 in speech (elementary 4.2, middle 3.7, high 4.0), thereby indicating high significance. At the same time, it is lower than the significance probability of 0.05 in debate (elementary 4.2, middle 3.9, high 4.0) and presentation (elementary 3.8, middle 3.4, high 3.5), thereby indicating low significance.

Table 8. Importance of persuasive competence by type of discourse

	Elementary	Middle	High	Total	F-value	p-value
Debate	4.2±.90	3.9±.92	4.0±.95	4.0±.93	4.729	.009*
Discussion	3.6±1.08	3.5±.89	3.5±.94	3.6±.96	.195	.823
Negotiation	3.9±1.15	3.9±.92	3.8±1.06	3.9±1.03	.204	.815
Presentation	3.8±1.06	3.4±.93	3.5±.82	3.5±.96	6.152	.002*
Speech	4.2±1.06	3.7±.95	4.0±1.00	3.9±1.01	7.164	.001**
Conversation	3.9±1.13	3.7±.85	3.8±.85	3.8±.94	1.385	.252
(Class) meeting	4.0±1.11	3.8±.89	3.7±.85	3.8±.96	2.174	.115

*p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001, Mean±SD

A correlation analysis was conducted to determine whether there was a correlation in each situation in terms of students' thoughts about the need for persuasive competence in the seven situations. Table 9 shows that, all seven situations had correlations with a value lower than the significance probability of 0.01, indicating high statistical significance. Moreover, the correlation analysis on students' thoughts about the need for persuasive competence in the seven situations showed that the coefficient of correlation between '(class) meeting' and 'speech' was .635, indicating a high positive correlation. In other words, the more students thought that persuasive competence was necessary in (class) meetings, the more they tended to think that it was also necessary in speeches.

Table 9. Correlation analysis of the need for persuasive competence by type of discourse

	Debate	Discussion	Negotiation	Presentation	Speech	Conversation	(Class) meeting
Debate	1	.402**	.422**	.356**	.508**	.287**	.387**
Discussion		1	.403**	.345**	.390**	.293**	.360**
Negotiation			1	.206**	.347**	.320**	.239**
Presentation				1	.518**	.433**	.492**
Speech					1	.368**	.635**
Conversation						1	.449**
(Class) meeting							1

*p<.05, **p<.01

4.3.2. Efficacy in detailed educational content

Table 10 shows the results on how students specifically evaluated the detailed persuasive competences on a five-point scale. First of all, using a one-way ANOVA test to determine whether there was a difference between school levels in thoughts on persuasive speech. It was found that all items except two—"I use valid (reasonable) grounds when persuading (I argue or object)" and "I think of the purpose of persuasion when persuading"—showed lower values than the significance probability of 0.001, thereby indicating high significance.

Overall, elementary school students rated their own competences in most items highly, while middle and high school students responded that they faced difficulty in competences related to information processing, emotional persuasion, and the use of media. The competences that high school students perceived as insufficient were related to communication and expression methods such as language use ethics, nonverbal use, consideration of the narrator's public confidence, and proper grammar use. The content achievement level presented by the national curriculum provides content related to expressions from the lower grades of elementary school, such as "expressing emotions," "looking at the listener," "using proper and refined language," and "using appropriate expressions, gestures and way of speech." However, these are too abstract and lack connectivity or sequence, which may have led to the difficulty in high school, despite being considered basic content. Therefore, educational content related to nonverbal or expressive strategies must be provided beginning in the lower grades and improved as the grades increase such that the content intensifies and is repeated.

Table 10. Self-evaluation about persuasive speech

Self-evaluation about persuasive speech	Elementary	Middle	High	Total	F-value	p-value
I use various and abundant grounds when persuading.	3.9±.89	3.4±.76	3.3±.95	3.5±.89	17.087	.000***
I use new and original arguments or grounds when persuading.	4.0±.85	3.4±.82	3.2±.99	3.5±.94	27.673	.000***
I get rid of content that interrupt my persuasive argument.	4.0±.83	3.4±.73	3.3±.96	3.5±.88	25.668	.000***
I use appropriate arguments when persuading.	4.2±.79	3.6±.76	3.5±.88	3.8±.85	25.642	.000***
I use valid (reasonable) grounds when persuading. (I argue or object.)	4.0±.91	4.1±4.75	3.6±3.07	3.9±3.52	.529	.590
I make my persuasive argument clear (definite).	4.4±1.86	3.8±1.69	3.5±.93	3.9±1.61	8.936	.000***
I organize the content of persuasion so that they reveal the key information well according to the flow of content (what to put at the beginning-middle-end).	4.1±.80	3.3±.81	3.2±1.00	3.5±.94	35.813	.000***
I think about the listener when persuading.	4.1±.85	3.6±.84	3.6±.94	3.7±.90	12.780	.000***
I think about the possibility of (the other's) objection or refutation when persuading.	4.2±.82	3.6±.83	3.2±1.04	3.6±.96	29.896	.000***
I respect the other when persuading.	4.6±4.88	3.8±.90	3.7±1.01	4.0±2.79	3.452	.033
I empathize with the other's emotions and respond adequately when persuading.	4.5±4.81	3.5±.88	3.5±.81	3.8±2.78	5.167	.006**
I thoroughly prepare the content of persuasion.	4.0±.88	3.4±.90	3.2±.94	3.6±.96	23.805	.000***
I think of the purpose of persuasion when persuading.	4.1±.82	3.9±2.55	3.6±.85	3.9±1.78	2.408	.091
I think of the process of persuasion when persuading.	4.1±.88	3.4±.88	3.3±.97	3.6±.97	27.187	.000***
I make appropriate use of words or terms when persuading.	4.0±.93	3.5±.90	3.4±.97	3.6±.96	14.384	.000***
I use grammatically correct language when persuading.	4.1±.92	3.5±.88	3.2±1.07	3.6±1.01	24.920	.000***
I persuade logically.	4.1±.89	3.5±.89	3.2±1.09	3.6±1.01	24.789	.000***
I appeal to emotions when persuading.	3.8±1.02	3.3±.91	3.1±.94	3.4±.99	15.156	.000***
I am trustworthy (to the other) when persuading.	4.0±.83	3.6±.82	3.3±1.03	3.7±.93	18.391	.000***
I use adequate pronunciation, speed, and tone when persuading.	3.9±.99	3.5±.82	3.3±.99	3.6±.96	12.914	.000***
I look at the other when persuading.	4.3±.78	3.7±.88	3.6±1.01	3.8±.93	17.220	.000***
I use adequate hand gestures when persuading.	3.8±1.02	3.5±.94	3.3±.95	3.5±.99	9.320	.000***
I show a confident attitude when persuading.	4.1±.96	3.6±.89	3.3±1.07	3.7±1.01	18.833	.000***
I comply with the order of speech or rules (time) when persuading.	4.1±.80	3.5±.88	3.4±.98	3.7±.94	23.959	.000***
I critically analyze and listen to (the other's) persuasive strategies and then persuade.	4.0±.93	3.4±.86	3.1±1.00	3.5±1.00	30.119	.000***
I listen while deciding whether content (about the other's arguments or views) is right, and persuade the other with my argument.	4.1±.89	3.5±.89	3.4±.91	3.7±.94	19.123	.000***
I effectively use content with media and materials (PPT or video clips) when persuading.	4.0±1.01	3.2±.99	3.2±.98	3.4±1.05	24.110	.000***
I think of how the results of persuasion will affect society when persuading.	4.1±.95	3.3±.88	3.1±1.05	3.5±1.02	30.504	.000***
I explore alternatives that will satisfy both parties in negotiations.	4.0±.91	3.6±.86	3.3±.95	3.7±.94	16.253	.000***
I adjust opinions presented in discussions.	4.1±.95	3.8±2.51	3.3±.91	3.7±1.80	5.709	.004**
I comply with procedures and rules in debates.	4.2±.85	3.6±.87	3.4±.95	3.7±.94	25.731	.000***
I use suitable persuasive strategies (methods) in a speech while thinking that it is important for the narrator to give trust to the other.	4.1±.88	3.6±.81	3.3±.94	3.7±.92	21.685	.000***

*p<.05 **p<.01 ***p<.001

5. CONCLUSION

As per the research findings, this paper offers implications on the educational content of persuasive speech to enhance the communicative competence of students, as well as recommendations for educational content. First, students' self-recognition of persuasive speech tended to decrease as their grades increased; thus, it is necessary to subdivide and specify education content that can be applied differentially considering the students' state. Second, there is a need for a curriculum that intensifies the core competences instead of one that limits certain content to a particular year, as content about participating in social community problems in terms of social aspects is presented in the ninth grade or higher when there is almost no opportunity for speech education. Third, the educational content of persuasive speech must be provided systematically by beginning in the lower grades and presenting content in the consecutive order of basic-development-application in light of the actual situation of education while also holistically developing persuasive competence. Fourth, teaching-learning methods or course plans for providing the content must also be reconsidered, as students lack confidence in cognitive matters. Fifth, it is necessary to focus on middle school students in persuasive speech education, who showed a huge gap in the efficacy of persuasive speech, by developing specific plans to provide in-depth persuasive speech education.

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